

D4.1 Specialisation and collaboration in the DIH universe

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About the DIHNET.EU project

The overall aim of DIHNET.EU is to create a sustainable European network of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), by developing a set of tools and boosting the collaboration of the different DIH networks, DIHs and other key DIH stakeholders in Europe. The project will act as a coordinator to enhance the collaboration, aligning and synchronizing their activities. This is considered crucial for a better support of SMEs and MidCap companies in offering and using digitisation services.

The project is carried out by TNO, Tecnalia, Fundingbox, euRobotics, BLUMORPHO and LuxInnovation, have strong experience in DIHs and well connected to the EU DIH community.

Preface to the deliverable

This deliverable is the first part of WP4 on reinforcement of specialisation. It will form basis for future work in this WP on finding mechanisms that support specialisation and collaboration in the DIH landscape. It will be shared with the DIH community and with policy-makers as a starting point for joint work on the development of common visions for specialisation strategies among the various initiatives on EU level. The deliverable aims to identify relevant questions and provide first thoughts on these questions. It also aims to identify the responsibilities among different actors in the DIH landscape.

The deliverable takes a broad look at specialisation and goes beyond the initially described work in two ways:

- DIHNET focuses primarily on networks of DIHs rather than on individual DIHs. In recent years the DIH landscape has become highly complex with a proliferation of hubs, the emergence of regional DIH networks, national platforms and pan-European networks of innovation hubs. This complexity requires us to look beyond individual hubs and assess specialisation not only in individual regions but also between regional national and international levels. The discussion and future assessment of demand for services and collaboration needs to be based on a comprehensive view of specialisation which presented in this deliverable. Thus, the deliverable outlines the basic conceptual framework that allows DIHs and DIH networks to consider the topic of specialisation.
- Based on this conceptual overview, we will work with selected (6-8) DIHs and networks in order to validate this approach and explore with them what possible strategies could be adopted to support specialisation and collaboration in the EU DIH landscape. This will be used to further the work in the upcoming tasks within the WP4 which aims to develop specialisation strategies (D4.4). The assessment of demand and regional assets will be done in an integrated manner building on recent work by the JRC, which has conducted two regional studies on the connection between smart specialisation and DIHs.

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1 Introduction

1.1 The European Context of the Digital Innovation Hubs landscape

Digital Innovation Hubs are a comparatively new initiative which can be traced back to 2015 and the discussion of pilot lines. Pilot lines were seen as a good mechanism to support companies in translating innovations to marketable products by not only providing technical but also business and ecosystem related services (Multi-KETs Pilot lines). In 2016 the Digitising European Industry Initiative (DEI) was launched with the aim to support the overall digitization of the European economy.¹ A key pillar of this initiative is the establishment of Digital Innovation hubs to support companies, and especially SMEs and start-ups, in tapping the potential of digital technologies.

Nowadays, the focus of the European Commission is to establish a **network of European DIHs** in which DIHs “collaborate to offer all necessary expertise to companies across Europe”.² The aim of such a network is to provide SMEs with access to expertise from an EU-wide network of hubs while at the same time ensuring the link to the regional ecosystem and enabling easy access to the digital support at close proximity. To achieve this aim the Commission envisions a co-funding mechanism in which the national and regional authorities will be responsible for the funding and support of new and existing DIHs while the EU supports the collaboration among hubs. At the moment, the Digital Europe Programme envisions that support will be provided for approximately 1 DIH per region. Yet, a question remains on how to ensure the collaboration among the European Hubs as well as how to ensure collaboration with already existing initiatives on EU level aiming to connect DIHs specialising in robotics (RODIN), AI (AI-DIH network), or sectoral networks (Smart Agri Hubs).

Ideally, a well-organized and cohesive DIH network will provide support to SMEs by offering access to specialised services, tailored to the regional needs, and based on local strengths (in specific sectors, technologies, or availability of infrastructure). Such a network could have the advantage of complementary partnerships (e.g. in the value chain or in supporting technologies) as well as possibilities to pool resources towards a common goal (e.g. through the initiative on Important Projects of Common European Interest (IPCEI)) to build the needed deep expertise, focus investments, and ultimately increase the quality of the services and technology infrastructures across Europe.

Yet, many questions remain regarding specialisation:

- At what level should specialisation take place – local, regional, national, supra-regional, European?
- Given that specialisation also requires collaboration, what is the added value for each of the stakeholders – within the hub, on regional, national and EU level – to collaborate?
- How to balance delivery of a range of services (one-top-shop) with the need for specialisation?
- What to specialise in – technology, sectors, focus (value chain integration or tech support) and how to select priorities?
- What services should be offered at different levels: DIH, regional networks, national platforms, EU networks?

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/pillars-digitising-european-industry-initiative>

² https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/system/files/ged/deibrochuremarch2018_3.pdf

- How to organize networks built on specialisation so that they can optimise their operation?

This report aims:

- To address the above questions in a coherent manner
- To inform stakeholders of the plans of the discussion regarding reinforced specialisation
- To provide ideas on the responsibilities of different actors in the DIH landscape

1.2 Structure of the report

The remainder of the report is structured as follows. Chapter 2 discusses in more detail the concept of specialisation, its rationale and it introduces the different types of specialisation. Chapter 3 addresses specialisation between different types of entities: DIHs, regional DIH networks, national networks and platforms, and European networks. This type of specialisation – presented here as ‘vertical specialisation’ – builds especially on earlier work of the consortium partners in I4MS and other European projects. Chapter 4 discusses ‘horizontal specialisation’ i.e. the priorities of hubs and networks with regard to technologies, sectors, issues and problems addressed in their respective regions or countries. This work builds not only on earlier discussions on DIH services and DIHs as a one-stop-shop, but also on the long tradition of smart specialisation work in Europe, notably the work done by JRC. Chapter 5 discusses how specialisation and collaboration can be supported. Chapter 6 presents some steps for DIH to develop smart specialisation strategies.

2 Specialisation: concept and rationale

2.1 The specialisation concept and DIH

Specialisation is an important concept in the economics and management literature. No organisation can offer everything to all clients and every organisation needs to set priorities and decide what it will and will not do. Specialisation provides focus and critical mass, thereby realising economies of scale. In turn this contributes to overall efficiency and effectiveness of the activities undertaken by the organisation.

Organisations can be more or less specialised. A supermarket offers a wide range of products to a variety of customers. But for special meat or vegetables a visit to the butcher and grocer is still required. Digital Innovation Hubs are seen as one-stop-shops for all clients in a region. But like all organisations they cannot provide everything to everyone. In practice they specialise on specific technologies (robotics hubs), sectors (Agrihubs) or on problems / solutions (e.g. health and ageing).

Specialisation also demands that DIH will deliver a (limited) number of services directly to clients. This depends on the size and the capabilities available at the hub. For more specialised types of requests the DIH will not do direct service delivery, but will act as brokers between specialised Competence Centres (possibly outside the region), or they will rely on specialised services provided by a regional DIH network or national platform. For instance it may not be feasible for all DIH to have solid expertise on IPR, but this expertise can effectively be provided by regional or national networks. Thus the one-stop-shop concept includes both direct service delivery and brokerage elements.

Still, these two notions of 1) specialisation on key technologies/services and a 2) acting as a broad one-stop-shop are difficult to reconcile. This is also confirmed by a recent report from the JRC studying 6 DIHs in different EU regions. The analysis concluded that DIHs are often struggling with finding “the balance between supporting basic and general forms of digitalisation efforts aimed at existing industries, and at the same time promoting the development of cutting-edge technological solutions in a niche of the market”.³

There is a need to resolve this tension. In this regard, the regional needs and available capabilities should be the leading principle for a DIH to prioritise its services and focus. In addition the following suggestions and observations can be made:

- **A mix of services.** Individual hubs provide some services directly and rely on regional network for more specialised services. Regional DIHs networks may offer a wide range of specialised services. For the rest of the activities, individual DIHs and regional DIH networks could act as a broker or a multi-sided platform to provide access to other more specialised services.
- **Integration is the other side of specialisation.** If entities are highly specialised, some of the services that they offer need to be integrated or aggregated at a higher level – so that they can be used by a wider group of clients. This may also require that some other organisation gives up part of its portfolio (in terms of technologies, services or skills), which is necessary

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https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC117976/jrc117976_dih6_case_studies_jrc_report_pubsy_online.pdf

to avoid duplication of service provision. But aligning portfolios of different organisations and agreeing on who does what may in practice be difficult to achieve

- Digital innovation hubs need to provide a **basic layer of services and capacities**. Such a basic set of services is needed in order to meet not only the specific technological needs of a 'client' but also inform them on new developments, and ensure that support can be provided to evaluate the underlying needs of their SME clients and eventually help SMEs in their digital transformation journey.
- Yet, in case there are several DIHs in a single region, attention should be paid to not over-complicate the ecosystem and to **avoid confusing the DIH 'client'** whom they should engage with.
- DIHs need to have **personnel with broad knowledge** and expertise in order to provide support and be able to cover the breadth (sectors, technologies, challenges, business models) and the depth of the requests from industry. This is a real challenge for many regions, especially the less advanced ones.
- At the same time, **DIHs should have access to specialised expertise** to be able to also support clients in their particular field of work. Such specialised expertise and solutions could be available in the DIH consortium, the broader regional ecosystem, or could be 'imported' from another region/country. It is therefore important that the DIH has established links in its ecosystem, acting as a spider in the web, connecting the relevant stakeholders.

2.2 DIH specialisation: needs and benefits

Currently a large number of DIHs (more than 280 fully operational and 200 in preparation) are active in the European landscape.⁴ Next to this, a wide range of activities and initiatives - such as smart specialisation platforms, IAs, CSAs, EIT, EBN, etc. - are also initiated on the EU level, leading to a complex picture with many inter-connected layers (figure 1). The overview becomes even more complicated when one adds closely related initiatives such as open innovation test-beds.

⁴ <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/digital-innovation-hubs-tool>

Figure 1 The European DIH landscape (TNO 2019)

Currently, there is little coordination among all these initiatives, which leads to lack of easy to find and complete information on technology offerings, expertise, capacities and infrastructure available outside the region, also leading to less effective coordination of efforts. In the end, this may result in overlapping investments and responsibilities among the actors in the ecosystem. Specialisation (on regional or DIH level) based on available assets and capabilities and needs is therefore essential. The following advantages of specialisation can be distinguished:

- **Responding to regional market demand for hub services:** Each region is likely to be confronted with varying challenges, requiring hubs to perform demand and needs assessment of the companies in their region in order to tailor their services. Most of the operating DIHs have performed a market assessment in one way or another. Examples are the 29 DIHs that prepared feasibility studies as part of I4MS phase 2. Many studies on different industries in a region are regularly performed and may serve as a basis for a hub to determine the needs of the region and how to address these.
- **Providing better (targeted) services:** DIHs as a one-stop shop, provide services and expertise to companies at close proximity. DIH tailor their service offering to the local needs (demand) and available capabilities (available capacity). Yet, digitisation is a broad and quickly developing field and it is impossible for any organization to have expertise in all technologies and/or domains. Collaborating in a network with specialised entities can ultimately offer access to specialised capacities from another region/country and improve the services offered to the SMEs and Mid-caps.
- **Creation of synergies on complementary technologies and expertise:** DIHs and regions can develop strategies for the future development of a specific technology/sector based on complementary expertise. This could be on different underlying technology, sector application, skills development. As not one single entity or in fact country could specialise and offer expertise on all possible technologies for all possible partners, collaboration based on complementary expertise and infrastructures will benefit all partners.
- **Support economies of scale:** while all DIHs are likely to offer a general basic level of common services and expertise, it is observed that some specialisation on technologies or sectors is

comparatively common, based the local assets and capabilities. By further focusing investments and efforts in these specialisation domains, DIHs can improve their expertise and also ensure that that they build on and focus their capacities, thus also increasing their potential market pool. This would also prevent scattering of skills and investments.

- **Avoid fragmentation and overlapping of investments in specialised and expensive infrastructure and capabilities:** investments in technological infrastructure is often costly to both establish and then maintain. Sharing such infrastructure can lead to more effective spending of public resources, optimise the utilization of the infrastructures, and ultimately enable access to state-of-the-art technology facilities.

3 Vertical specialisation at different levels⁵

3.1 Specialisation among the different entities in the EU DIH landscape

As mentioned the EU DIH landscape is quite complex and multi-layered. Discussing the responsibilities and the specialisation of the different players is therefore important in order to establish a good overview and facilitate better knowledge and information sharing.

3.2 Individual DIHs

Individual DIHs are often built around a competence centre (or have a link with one) and have built additional competences around the technology expertise. DIHs often focus on a particular technology or domain but often involve multiple partners in order to be able to offer a full services portfolio (including ecosystem, technology and business support services) to the local ecosystem.

The scope and specific services of the individual DIHs need to reflect the local needs and company demand. In this respect, the DIHs should develop an ecosystem analysis that maps not only available competences and functions of the different entities, but also mapping and analysis of the regional market, sectors and companies (including large companies and existing value chains as well as general characteristics of SMEs). Public consultations could prove a useful source of information but the capacities of some of the hub partners, such as SME or sector organizations and clusters, should also be utilized.

Yet, the very nature of DIHs as multi-entity organizations, make governance of the hubs complex. Specialisation and decision making on responsibilities among the DIH partners is not easy and requires negotiation. It can be expected that some degree of competition among the partners (who probably already existed in the region) for basic services would still remain. Therefore, it is key to develop a common vision of the DIH in which the individual partners recognize themselves and to which they contribute and collaborate.

It is also important to recognise that individual DIHs need not only to determine what services they will offer based on local demand, but also within their consortium identify which organization will focus on which priorities. Further, it should be clarified for which services the hub partners might offer similar services and compete.

Forming a common mind-set and identity for the hub and managing the tensions related to specialisation among the hub consortium could already be considered as a challenge. Resolving these tension points and managing the responsibilities of each of the individual partners within the hub can be a challenging and time consuming task, usually dealt with in the governance of the hub. A model for responsibilities, services and task, and payment arrangements needs to be considered to avoid

⁵ This sections builds on , Butter, M., Gijsbers, G. Goetheer, A., Karanikolova, K. (forthcoming) "Digital Innovation Hubs and Their Position in the European, National and Regional Innovation Ecosystems", in Denise Feldner (ed.), Chapter in: 'Redesigning Organizations - Concepts for the Connected Society', Butter, M., & Karanikolova, K. (2018), "Support to development of a basque digital innovation Hub", TNO report, Project reference code: 931101;
Butter, M, Karanikolova, K., Gijsbers, G. (2019), "Development of Digital Innovation Hubs | Final report", report for the development of a DIH in Trondheim, TNO 2019 R10324;
Karanikolova, K. Butter, M. (2019), "Development of Digital Innovation Hubs", report for GAIN,

friction among the partners and to ensure that SMEs can indeed receive support combining the expertise of the individual partners.

3.3 Regional DIH networks

Some regions have started to organize the activities of hubs in a more coordinated manner. These regional networks are mostly not technology or domain specific. Rather, they provide coordination of and support for individual hubs. Such coordination of nodes, allows a regional DIH network to address multiple sectors and/or technologies.

This however implies that some of the functions of the different hubs are taken over by this additional layer of regional network / hub. Some of these functions could be common services, connected to, for example, general dissemination and awareness activities, brokerage and general info on funding for instance. This has the advantage of offering a common window (one-stop-shop) for industry and also for coordinating activities and reduction of duplication of efforts on common services. The coordinator of such a regional entity should be independent to ensure that the interests of all individual DIH nodes are taken into account. The regional DIH networks should also be represented by a (team) of experts who can evaluate a problem as reported by a DIH and consider which technology or solution offered by which DIH node could provide support. Note that this means that the one-stop shop function is now provided by the regional DIH network, rather than the individual hub.

The regional DIH network would therefore not by itself be specialised, but its nodes can provide the needed specialised expertise or infrastructure. Cooperation with other regional networks could also be part of the activities of such entities as they would be able to engage on more strategic agenda setting on cross-regional level. For this, it is crucial to have a good overview of the infrastructures as well as the strengths and demand in the region.

Economies of scale can be achieved by combining some of the services that the individual DIH nodes would otherwise provide. Examples could be:

- common overview of funding instruments,
- road-mapping,
- participation in events with SMEs to generate awareness and interest (e.g. booths in technology fairs),
- disseminating information on upcoming national and EU policies,
- proposal writing,
- identification of cross-cutting topics in which DIH nodes could learn from each other

The precise sharing of services will depend on the particular regional situation – are the DIH nodes on close proximity, do they offer complementary, competing or unrelated technologies, do they have similar target audience (e.g. high-tech SMEs vs. late adopters).

Regional DIH networks can be seen as well positioned to broker, and then lead projects with DIHs (or networks) on cross-regional level. The advantage of such scenario for the individual SME is clear – the SME can get access to expertise not available in its region while relying on its regional DIH network to lead the project, find and interact with the relevant outside hub and also find possible complementarities with CCs or hubs nodes within the region. For the regional DIH network, collaboration with other entities and project management might be a service offered both to the SME

and the DIH nodes as well as mandate from the regional authorities. For the individual DIH nodes, the advantage is that they do not need to seek complementary competence outside the region and can outsource some of the project management responsibilities.

Regional DIH networks also have the advantage of being conveniently connected to the idea of one European DIH per region. Yet, a significant problem is the requirement that the supported European DIHs should focus on solutions using the priority technologies (AI, HPC, cyber and skills) which might not **necessarily** fit with the more generic nature of the regional DIH network or the regional needs.

3.4 IAs/CSA/existing EU Networks

Currently, one can see that activities are already ongoing to develop networks on hubs specialising in a tech of a sector. These are often led by CSA or IA activities and connect hubs on specialised topics such as AI, robotics, additive manufacturing, photonics, agro-food, health, etc. This presents yet another level above the regional networks.

Figure 2: EU network services (TNO)

It is however crucial to note that **the main audience in these networks are the DIHs and the regional DIH networks** (rather than the SMEs as is the case with DIHs). Therefore, these networks also have a different purpose – namely coordination and collaboration on EU level. The services offered by such networks also differ from those of individual hubs (see figure 2).

Individual DIHs and their CCs are likely to be interested in collaborative research, the business services and some of the ecosystem services such as a market place and EU strategy development. For DIH networks and even national programmes (such as the Mittelstand 4.0-Kompetenzzentrum) are likely to be interested in the ecosystem services, smarter specialisation, development of common tech approaches and to also some of the business services. Naturally, such networks indirectly provide value also to companies which might be interested in (and even pay for) participation in EU value chains and EU market places. Such networks offer representation on EU level but this could also create friction with the more general representation offered by the regional networks.

In order to establish a good service portfolio however, it is first needed to develop a good overview of the existing networks. This is not an easy task as many new projects with similar aims have been started and updating is time consuming. Further, there is a need to map activities (infrastructure, value chains currently ongoing, and even existing collaborations).

3.5 Overview of the responsibilities and services of the different initiatives

As outlined above, the different initiatives and entities in the EU DIH landscape have different responsibilities. These are very much dependent on the local situation, the local demand, existence of initiatives and leading stakeholder and specialisation of the entities. In general, the following categorization of responsibilities in terms of services can be summarised (see figure 3). White text indicates possible services for the particular type of initiatives, grey services that are not of interest. This overview can then be further explored in consultation with regional authorities.

Service CC	Service DIH node	Service reg. DIH network	Services Pan-EU
Community building	Community building	Community building	EU market place
Strategy development	Strategy development	Strategy development	EU awareness creation
Ecosystem learning	Ecosystem learning	Ecosystem learning	EU strategy development
Representation, promotion	Representation, promotion	Representation, promotion	Representation on EU level
Strategic RDI	Strategic RDI	Strategic RDI	EU widening and sharing expertise
Contract research	Contract research	Contract research	Creating common approaches
Technical support on scale-up	Technical support on scale-up	Technical support on scale-up	Pan-EU collaborative research
Provision of technology infrastructure	Provision of technology infrastructure	Provision of technology infrastructure	Standardization
Testing and validation	Testing and validation	Testing and validation	Smart(er) specialization
Incubator/accelerator support	Incubator/accelerator support	Incubator/accelerator support	Pan-EU value chain creation
Access to finance	Access to finance	Access to finance	EU industry market assessment
Skills and education	Skills and education	Skills and education	Pan-EU innovation fund
Project development	Project development	Project development	Organizing trans-regional collaboration
Offering housing	Offering housing	Offering housing	
		Pan-EU Collaboration	

Figure 3: Functions of the different initiatives, (white indicates interest) - TNO 2019

3.6 Funding innovation hubs and networks at different levels⁶

3.6.1 Regions

On **regional level**, the basic objective of the regional authorities is to optimise the use of existing capacities (existing infrastructure, partners, etc) in order to provide the optimum support for the regional companies. Therefore, the specialisation should take into account the regional market demand and the industrial focus.

While regions have access to ERDF funding, they can rarely invest in new infrastructure and in general their capital is scarce. Therefore, it is difficult for regions to support many different entities and divide their resources. Within the planning of the DEP, it is also expected that one DIH per region would be chosen to receive co-funding from EU and national/regional agencies. This creates further pressure on regions which might need to balance this choice of supporting one DIH with the need to address

⁶ Butter, M., & Karanikolova, K. (2018), "Support to development of a Basque digital innovation Hub", TNO report, Project reference code: 931101;

the needs of the different sectors within the region and ensuring future competitiveness. Choosing among priorities to specialise on can therefore be difficult.

For individual hubs, the priorities of selected by regions (maybe in collaboration with the DIH) are key in securing future ERDF support and funding support via the DEP.

3.6.2 National governments

On **national level**, specialisation among different regions within the country can support the trans-regional collaboration, thus offering for instance access to specific infrastructures (thus reducing investment needs). National governments are interested in investing in strategic infrastructures as well as in supporting the R&D policy for the country. Therefore, DIHs and regional DIH networks might consider this when choosing to invest in particular sectors that might require a large investment in infrastructures. While utilizing these infrastructures by allowing access to foreign users might in some cases be desirable (some sectors such as defence might be seen as national security), funding for R&D in another country is problematic for both infrastructure and research capacities.

3.6.3 EU level

On **EU level**, specialisation in infrastructure and skills provides the benefits of focusing investment while also supporting the development of excellence pockets within EU and boosting EU global leadership. To ensure subsidiarity and equal access, pan-EU access to such highly specialised infrastructures needs to be ensured.

Looking at the other services, collaboration on strategy development and identification of future opportunities could also streamline the priorities and funding on EU level. Sharing of good practices and examples could also be seen as a multiplier effect, supporting the overall development of the Single Market.

Specialisation can also play a role in establishing sustainable collaborations across Europe, stimulating cross-border, cross-industry and interdisciplinary innovations. The EU added value of such collaboration is thus seen as important and the DEP programme intends to address this EU added value of collaboration. From EU perspective, this collaboration and laying the foundations of the tools for collaboration can be the responsibility of the future European DIHs. Naturally, this would require that these DIHs have the appropriate support, framework, resources and mandate to bring collaboration a step further.

4 Horizontal specialisation

Following the discussion above on specialisation and allocation of tasks between different levels of administration, this section focuses on the substantive priorities that need to be selected by different DIH and networks. This builds to a large extent on the work on smart specialisation.

4.1 Smart Specialisation Strategies and Digital Innovation Hubs

Smart specialisation is one of the main specialisation and collaboration mechanism currently in place in Europe. Efforts have been made to support regions to collaborate on common challenges and in common industries. An examples are the Smart Specialisation platforms and the respective various partnerships (more than 30) active across Europe. The Vanguard initiatives is another example. These existing initiatives should be taken as good examples on how to identify and enter into partnerships based on priorities identified in various regions. Building on their efforts and already existing mapping of expertise and interests of various regions per topic, further collaboration could be stimulated.

Many DIHs are connected to the S3 strategies in their countries and a recent report from JRC also points that many DIHs are also participating in the consultation processes or even the drafting of the S3 strategies. This becomes ever more important with the DEP and the need to select a DIH per region.

To identify how DIHs can determine their specialisation and collaboration strategies as well as to support regions to collaborate, there is first a need to provide some clarification of the challenges present. This note aims to list some of the issues with the intent to then develop recommendation on steps to identify and determine areas of specialisation within the region.

Smart Specialisation Strategies are a pre-requisite for receiving ERDF funds. They are formed following an entrepreneurial discovery process, building on the assets already available in a region and the potential for future development. They reflect the regional perspective but are, almost by definition, place-based strategies.

An important part of the Smart Specialisation Strategies is that the ERDF is part of the EU Cohesion policy, aiming to support overall economic growth in Europe, reduce differences among regions by supporting less developed ones and also find possible collaborations based on specialisation strategies developed by each individual country/region.

4.2 Different parameters for specialisation

Horizontal specialisation can be achieved along different lines:

- Often, specialisation is based on **technologies**, reflecting the origin of many hubs as university or RTO initiatives. Robotics, AI, IoT, HPC, Cyber-Physical Systems, simulation and modelling and additive manufacturing are important technology bases for DIHs.
- Other hubs specialise on **sectors**, these may be more **business-oriented**. A sectoral or business orientation often reflects regional assets, capabilities and needs. Networks of DIHs focusing on a sector such as agri-food sector have come up in recent years.
- Further specialisation can be seen along **the value chain**, where hubs would specialise on specific links in the chain, e.g. DIHs focusing on materials research could find useful

collaboration with DIHs using 3D printing. In relation to collaboration, specialisation is likely to succeed only if complementarities in the specialisation of the DIHs are found. There are already efforts in Europe to form a network of DIHs specialising on robotics or AI, or any other tech.

- Other hubs address specific combinations of technologies and **domain needs**. For example the IA DIH HERO aims to develop a network among DIHs focusing on robotics for healthcare.

Specialising in technologies brings the advantage of possible application in multiple sectoral or other domains. Some basic technological advances could be adjusted and applied in multiple sectors (e.g. robotics). Others could be relevant for only part of the supply chain and therefore highly dependent on the existing corporate ecosystem (e.g. flexible electronics) but have multiple applications further in the value and supply chain. Yet, this specialisation needs to be coupled with a good understanding of the needs of the different sectors (potential clients).

One disadvantage of specialising in a specific technology is that it may support technology push. SMEs might find it difficult to determine which technology they need or might not even know what the technology implies. In these cases, it is important that a DIH (or a network) is able to support the DIH in finding the best solution for their problem, irrespective of technology.

Specialisation by sector brings the advantage of easy recognition by SMEs of particular sector issues. Yet, a sector might need a number of technologies to provide digital solutions, implying that the DIH should have access to a broad network of specialised experts or other hubs. Following only sectorial specialisation can be problematic as it may miss opportunities outside the sector.

Specialisation could also be on the value chain if a regional supply and value chain are of particular importance. The specialisation would then be on one or a few selected links in the chain. An example would be materials developers collaborating with 3D printing machinery developers or networks.

It can be concluded that the **specialisation is likely to occur in matrix form** in which DIHs specialise to a certain extent on both technologies, and on sectors, or maybe on links in the value chain. Some DIHs will be focusing a bit more on the technology or the sector depending on the regional needs and maybe even the value chain focus of the local industry.

How to organize the collaboration given this complex specialisation overview is a challenging question. In order to find the right partner to collaborate with, one is likely to want to know the strengths of the partner (their specialisation), including some examples of success stories that back up their credibility. On the other hand, the search of a partner should not be overly complicated and should not require too much time.

5 Supporting collaboration and specialisation

The above discussion outlines the complexity of specialisation and the different benefits and effects it could have. Choosing priorities is however not easy. There are still a number of unknowns such as how is specialisation currently chosen in the DIHs, but also who is responsible for priority setting – both at the level of individual hubs and networks at and regional and country level. Is it centrally decided or is it a result of a bottom up process? Should specialisation be promoted, or should be allowed to emerge organically as the DIHs further develop and mature? Is there actually a market need to offer information on such specialisation, or are the DIHs focusing more on basic technology solutions at the moment – for which there is a limited need for specialisation.

All these questions lead to the conclusion that a common framework for analysing and discussing specialisation is needed. To facilitate this discussion, one **needs a good overview of the existing competences and expertise in Europe.**

The JRC Catalogue is a good first step that provides basic information on the existing DIHs in Europe. Yet, the catalogue has some shortcomings, including its less dynamic nature and the uncertainty on how the Catalogue will be connected to the newly-proposed European DIHs. Therefore, it is important that mapping of existing expert capacity infrastructures is included in the future work of the Commission. Such mapping has already started in some of the smart specialisation platforms and different projects are also mapping their internal competences. Coordination and establishment of a database that connects partners in the catalogue to infrastructures and possibly already established collaborations can support industry to more easily find needed information.

DIHs are meant to be a one-stop-shop for companies and help them to test before they invest. It is impossible though to cover all technologies and offer all additional competences. Therefore, it is suggested that a mapping of the focus of hubs should not only address technologies and sectors, but also the priorities in relation to links in **the value chain.**

It is crucial that different databases are coordinated on EU level. Currently, different initiatives such as test beds and KETs centres are being mapped and monitored separately from DIHs. It will benefit all stakeholders if **all these mapping databases are connected and coordinated** (this would also facilitate information updates) and at least a common structure of the information collected is established. This can also support regions in identifying existing capabilities that can be used for the future development of a specialisation strategy.

6 Developing specialisation strategies for DIHs and networks

The discussions on specialisation and collaboration within and between regions are often complex and are heavily dependent on the regional situation. Consequently, there is no “right” or “one-fits-all” solution. Some ideas and support on how to develop define and refine a hub’s strategy to specialisation and collaboration can be found in the RIS3 Guide⁷ for the development of regional smart specialisation strategies. When coupled with the observations on specialisation and collaboration of DIHs, the following steps can be distinguished:

- Analysis of the regional context and existing inter-consortium capabilities
 - Regional assets evaluation, including specifically looking at the capacities and the strengths of the consortium partners participant in the DIH. This should be followed by a general overview of the strengths and weaknesses of the region and identifying bottlenecks. These bottlenecks and weaknesses might present opportunities for future services of the hubs.
A thorough evaluation of the market and its competitive position of the region and the various industries can be performed within the DIH consortium, utilizing tools such as SWOT analysis, regional profiling studies, surveys. But it is important that these preliminary analysis is then validated with the ecosystem, via for example workshops with relevant stakeholders from industry and other supporting organizations (see for example steps 2 and 5 in I4MS Mentoring material on ‘building a business plan’).⁸
- Ecosystem assessment to identify other relevant partners, users and suppliers: the ecosystem analysis might build on the different functions of the organizations present (see I4MS Mentoring material on ecosystem analysis).
- This analysis should be expanded with the outward dimension,⁹ taking into account what other regions are specialising in but also networks in which the hub might already be part of (on national or EU level). Further, DIHs and regions should take into account the existence of already functioning initiatives as well as similar hub services offered in close proximity.
- Demand assessment of regional ecosystem, including:
 - Analysis of regionally active industries
 - Prevailing sectors and their digital maturity
 - Characterisation of the different industries – number of entities, competitive position of the main actors with respect to other regions, possibilities to expand or participate in value chains and mapping of these value chains to support DIH clients with market analysis.
 - Cluster analysis, value chain analysis, as well as analysis of possible futures markets where current industries can expand or re-invent themselves.
 - Assessment of demand for DIH services: there is a need for DIHs to continuously monitor whether they continue to offer added value to the ecosystem and that they are not overcrowding the market with unnecessary services. This requires close connection to the DIH customers, evaluation surveys, interviews with key

⁷ <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/s3-guide>

⁸ <https://i4ms.eu/mentoring-programme/business-plan/exploring-interest>

⁹ <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/interactive-ris3-guide/-/wiki/Main/PART+III+Step+1>

stakeholders and seeking feedback. One good practice is to utilize existing services and organizations already actively participating in the region and determine what further services might be needed. Ensuring variety in the consulted customers is key.

- Assessment of possible partnerships: Based on the assessment of the regional assets and the outward assets, DIHs might map potential partnerships with other DIHs or networks for example on topics at an early research/development stage or topics where high capital investments are needed e.g. in HPC capacities.
- Outlining responsibilities and deciding on provision (or not) of common services: as mentioned above, the discussion on the division of responsibilities and services among the individual DIHs, the regional DIH networks, and EU collaborations needs to be carefully considered. The following considerations need to be taken into account.
 - The process of how these responsibilities can be divided depends on the regional needs and available resources as well as the interests of the individual entities.
 - This agreement, aggregation and economies of scale will also depend on the maturity of the hubs existing in the region as well as the general digital maturity of the region and the existing industries.
 - A third factor is the willingness to collaborate as well as the presence of a leading entity or organization which might take the initiative and support the collaboration and division of responsibilities. This might well be a regional authority or a partner that participates in more than one DIH.